

THETIDA

Technologies and methods for improved resilience and sustainable preservation of underwater and coastal cultural heritage to cope with climate change, natural hazards and environmental pollution

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D.6.2: Midterm Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation Activities

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Abstract

The THETIDA project approaches safeguarding and protecting Europe's coastal and underwater cultural heritage from the effects of climate change and natural hazards in a holistic manner that includes risk management, protection and preparedness, as complementary strategies to prevent damages to CH sites, identify and ward off additional threats and promote policy tools for climate neutrality and economic resilience in coastal areas. THETIDA project achieves this goal through the development of a preventive conservation strategy that includes monitoring, risk preparedness and management, for underwater and coastal CH (U&C-CH) sites, identify and ward off additional threats and promote adaptation, reconstruction and other post-disruption strategies to restore normal conditions to the historic area, as well as long-term strategic approaches to adapt to CC and to wield policy tools for economic resilience. In this project, an interdisciplinary team of researchers, experts and practitioners will develop, test and validate an integrated multiple heritage risk assessment and protection system with evidence-based monitoring frameworks, innovative tools and instruments and through participatory processes (Citizens' Science and Living Labs). The project implementation actions will link the social innovations with cutting-edge technologies (ICT and IoT harmonised tools).

Consortium

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Disclaimer of warranties

This document is part of the deliverables from the project THETIDA, which has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement 101095253.

This project has used a standard methodology already developed in the e-shape project (Grant Agreement number: 820852), following EU recommendations. Ad hoc modifications were added to comply with the conditions of the Grant Agreement for THETIDA project (Grant Agreement number: 101095253).

The information and views set out in this deliverable are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf may be held responsible for the use which may be made of the following information.

Executive Summary

The present document reports the communication and dissemination activities carried out over the last 18 months, from May 2023 to October 2024, and aims to highlight how the impact of the THETIDA project was maximised through communication and dissemination activities, and the exploitation of the project was anticipated. It was developed in accordance with D6.1 Early Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan and Activities [1].

Considering the objectives, audiences, and key messages presented in D6.1, WP6 partners implemented carefully elaborated communication and dissemination strategies through selected channels and tools [1]. From M01 to M18, activities were focused primarily on awareness raising and community growth, targeting simultaneously primary end-users of the solutions developed in the project, stakeholders indirectly impacted by the results of the project, and citizens (target audiences n°1, 2 and 3).

To achieve this objective, high-impact activities were led both online, on the website and social media platforms of the project, and offline with the organisation of and participation to authoritative events, while leveraging the variety of channels and tools available to THETIDA consortium partners.

Complementing the updates of the communication and dissemination activities, D6.2 introduces the progresses of the exploitation strategy, and introduces the Business Model Canvas established within the framework of Task 6.4.

The evaluation section of the document reveals the fruitful and encouraging outcomes of the communication and dissemination activities implemented over the first 18 months of the project. To ensure the effective achievement of the KPIs targeted by the end of the project, mitigation measures were rigorously devised for unreached targets. It should be noted that some targets mentioned in the Grant Agreement are ambitious and challenging to reach. The difficulty was reported to the Project Coordinator in the early stages of the project.

This document should be understood as a living document and will be updated for each planned reporting period. It will be complemented by D6.3 Final Dissemination, Communication, and Exploitation Plan and Activities.

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Abbreviations & Acronyms

Abbreviation / acronym	Description
CNAS	Portuguese National Centre for Nautical and Underwater Archaeology
D6.1	Deliverable number 6 belonging to WP 1
D6.2	Deliverable number 6 belonging to WP 6
EC	European Commission
EGU	European Geosciences Union
RescueME	Resilient Cultural Landscapes
STECCI	Stone monument ensembles and the climate change impact
UCH	Underwater Cultural Heritage
WP	Work Package

1. Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the Document

Deliverable (D) 6.2 “Midterm Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan and Activities” aims to provide updates on the activities led during the first 18 months of project implementation. D6.2 is based on and furthers the strategies stated within D6.1 Early Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan and Activities (D6.1) [1].

1.2 Intended Readership

D6.2 is primarily intended to be disseminated to consortium partners and reviewers of the THETIDA project. External individuals with an *ad-hoc* interest are invited to read the deliverable. The deliverable will be available on the [THETIDA website](#)¹ and on the [Zenodo platform](#)².

1.3 Document Structure

D6.2 begins with a chapter dedicated to reporting the implementation of the initial communication and dissemination plan from May 2023 to October 2024, presenting the communication and dissemination activities undertaken, and updates on the channels and tools. The first chapter continues the reporting by presenting the progress made from May 2023 to October 2024 on the exploitation strategy and particularly the first draft of the Business Model Canvas. The second chapter focuses on the evaluation of the communication and dissemination activities undertaken during the first half of the project. Reflecting on the first two chapters, the concluding chapter sets the way forward for the next period of the project regarding communication and dissemination activities.

¹ <https://thetida.eu/#/outputs>

² <https://zenodo.org/communities/thetida>

2. Midterm Report on Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation Plan

Considering the objectives, targets, and key messages stated within D6.1, THETIDA has implemented a coherent Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation Plan over the first 18 months of the project [1].

Communication, dissemination and exploitation activities are deeply intertwined as they target similar audiences at different scales and are used to promote each other in a virtuous circle. As an illustration, communication activities help creating an online community interested in the dissemination of the results of the project. On another hand, both communication and dissemination activities support the exploitation of the project by putting forward the achievements of the project, creating a pool of potential stakeholders and end-users, and by enabling the uptake and or further development of solutions by relevant audiences. The different audiences targeted can be found in table 1.

Table 1. Summary of THETIDA Audiences from D6.1 [1]

Target audience n°1	Target audience n°2	Target audience n°3
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Cultural heritage related SMEs and industries; • Policy makers at European, national and local level involved in Maritime Spatial planning and cultural heritage conservation. This includes national authorities and national administrative bodies (e.g., Ministry of Culture), regional authorities and regional governmental bodies (e.g., provinces, regional water boards), local administrators (e.g, municipalities, local park authorities). • Academia and research community (including professional experts groups of scientists, heritage experts, 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Environmental monitoring agencies; • Fishery authorities; • Search and rescue agencies; • Financing institutions; • Entities involved in remote-sensing and in-situ sensors; • Climate risk monitoring experts. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tourism operators and representatives of tourism industry; • General public (including tourists, residents, etc.) • Diving centres and divers.

<p>research institutes and experts);</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Coastal and underwater archaeologists; • Site managers; • Technical chambers; • Product developers and users. 		
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2.1 Updated Communication Activities

The communication activities and strategies presented in D6.2 are ongoing actions from May 2023 to October 2024. During this period, WP6 focused on raising awareness on the project and on growing the community of interest around the project. The activities undertaken reflect the main objectives of the period.

Communication activities included:

1. The creation of dedicated promotional material presenting the project such as flyers, brochures, posters, and banners, as presented in D6.1 [1].
2. The update of the presentations of the THETIDA pilot sites on the website to provide additional details to online visitors on the culture and history of the sites, the challenges faced, and the solutions provided by THETIDA.
3. The update of the website was followed by a communication campaign on the seven THETIDA pilot sites. The campaign aimed to create a direct link between THETIDA social media channels and website to enhance traffic towards the website and leverage the online community of the project. It simultaneously enabled an increase of the online community with local stakeholders. From 10 November 2023 to 29 December 2023, total followers gained: 107 (622 at M07 to 729 at M08). The three audiences of the THETIDA project were targeted.
4. Ongoing social media campaign on international days to capitalise on the momentum created by international days and promote the multi-disciplinary approach of the project. The campaign targets the communities involved in the different days (*e.g.*, World Ocean Day, International Day of Monuments and Sites, World Environment Day) and enable a broad outreach of the project. The primary targets are audience n°1 and 3.
5. Social media campaign using the hashtag #ZoomOn and a specific template in accordance with the visual identity of the project (Fig. 1). It aims to create outreach towards projects, initiatives, events, of relevance to the THETIDA project. The social campaign started in January 2024 and is ongoing. It targets the three audiences of the THETIDA project.

Figure 1. Illustration of the #ZoomOn Campaign

6. Social media campaign introducing the tools and methodologies used and developed in the project from 26 January 2024 to 26 March 2024. The campaign aimed to provide a better understanding of the project to the online community, reaching out to more technical communities (target audiences n°1 and 2). Total followers gained: 194 (766 in M09, 960 in M11).
7. Consortium partners attended an online networking event organised by the BCThubs project on 8 November 2023 to present the THETIDA project and connect with other Horizon and EU-funded projects.
8. Establishment of the Green Cluster for Cultural Heritage with the Climate Effect EU projects THETIDA, TRIQUETRA, RescueME, and STECCI to coordinate actions and activities to maximise the impact of the projects. The Green Cluster for Cultural Heritage aims to facilitate knowledge exchange and best practices among partners projects to efficiently preserve Europe's heritage against the effects of climate change. While each of the project focuses on a specialized expertise, the Cluster enables each of the Climate Effect EU projects to benefit from a broadened community of researchers and cultural heritage actors to strengthen the dissemination of the results and ensure optimal benefits of the research carried in Europe and beyond.
9. A session dedicated to communication activities of project partners of the Green Cluster for Cultural Heritage was organised during EGU General Assembly 2024.
10. Publication of 31 blog articles on the THETIDA website.

11. THETIDA was mentioned in the European Commission publication on ‘Driving a Green, Digital & Innovative European Cultural Heritage’ (January 2024) (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. European Commission publication on ‘Driving a Green, Digital & Innovative European Cultural Heritage’ p.14

2.2 Updated Dissemination Activities

In line with the targeted audiences identified within D6.1, the dissemination activities have been focusing on target audience n°1 [1].

Section 2.2 of the present D6.2 is based on the reports collected from consortium partners in the first 18 months of the project. On a monthly basis, partners were asked to complete a table summarizing the latest dissemination activities undertaken.

During the reporting period, partners have taken part in 58 events detailed below.

2.2.1 Activities carried from M01 to M18

As of 1st October 2024, the following dissemination activities were reported to WP6 leader:

1. Events organised by demo leaders included:

- 16 training sessions: on technical diving and the THETIDA project, organised by IANTD during the Summer 2023 in Italy.
- Organisation of a series of activities by CCVAlg during the Week of Science and Technology (*Semana da Ciência e Tecnologia*) in October 2023 to raise awareness on the impact of climate change on the Portuguese pilot site and on the THETIDA project, in Faro, Portugal.
- Meeting organised by UAlg in June 2024 with the University of Cadiz and two members of the Nautical and Underwater Archaeology (CNANS and RECON Offshore) to present the THETIDA project, exchange knowledge, and plan diving activities on the Algarve pilot site in Faro, Portugal.
- 2 diving events organised by IANTD in Fiumaretta (Italy) in July 2024.

2. Presentations in scientific conferences

- Overall presentation of the THETIDA project at Cyprus Bicomunal Sustainability Conference (October 2023). Partner involved: CMMI.
- Presentation of the THETIDA smart buoy at CyMON 2024, Larnaca, Cyprus (February 2024). Partner involved: CMMI.
- Overall presentation of the THETIDA project at the Panhellenic Conference on Digital Cultural Heritage 2024, Larisa, Greece. Partners involved: CMMI and ICCS (March 2024).
- Presentation of the THETIDA project at the Primary School of Gonnoi, Larisa, Greece. Partners involved: CMMI and ICCS (March 2024)
- Presentation on shipwreck archaeology in the Eastern Mediterranean at the 8th Conference on Scientific Diving (ECSD8), Heraklion, Crete (April 2024). Partner involved: UCY.
- Encontro de Oceanografia of Associação Portuguesa de Oceanografia (APOCEAN), Peniche, Portugal (May 2024). Partners involved: UAlg, CIMA, CCVAlg. 2 presentations:
 - Mendonça, F., Martins, F., Bertino, L. (2024). Data Assimilation Tools Towards Coastal Operational Models
 - Mills, L., Garzon, J. and Martins, F. (2024). Operational modeling of the Algarve coast and monitoring with autonomous underwater vehicles (AUVs) to evaluate risk spots for submerged cultural heritage.
- THALASSA 2024 – Marine Sciences Conference, Larnaca, Cyprus, (May 2024):
 - Fostering resilience of coastal and underwater cultural heritage to address emerging climatic risks Panagiotis Michalis, Claudio Mazzoli,

Vassilia Karathanassi, Deniz Ikiz Kaya, Flavio Martins, Michele Cocco, Anaïs Guy, Paschalina Giatsiatsou, Angelos Amditis.

- IEEE International Symposium on Geoscience and Remote Sensing (IGARSS), Athens, Greece (July 2024): Session CCS.44: Geoscience and Remote Sensing for Cultural Heritage Protection led by THETIDA. 2 presentations:
 - Integrated Sensing Solutions for Monitoring Heritage Risks, Lampros Pavlopoulos, Panagiotis Michalis, Marios Vlachos, Anastasios Georgakopoulos, Chrysovalantis Tsiakos, Angelos Amditis.
 - THETIDA: Enhanced Resilience and Sustainable Preservation of Underwater and Coastal Cultural Heritage, Panagiotis Michalis, Claudio Mazzoli, Vassilia Karathanassi, Deniz Ikiz Kaya, Flavio Martins, Michele Cocco, Anaïs Guy, and Angelos Amditis.
- EnOLL Open Living Labs Days 2024, Timisoara, Romania (September 2024): THETIDA – Living Labs for inclusive and innovative climate risk monitoring of cultural heritage. Partners involved: TU/e.
- 4 presentations at EGU General Assembly 2024 (April 2024) Session CL3.2.2 Heritage exposed to climatic and natural hazards: identification, quantification and mitigation of evolving risks:
 - Oliveira, S., Veiga-Pires, C., Ikiz Kaya, D., Michalis, P., & Mazzoli, C. (2024, mars). Unveiling End Users Needs and Requirements for Coastal and Underwater Heritage Sites under the impacts of Climate Change. EGU General Assembly 2024 (EGU), Vienna, Austria. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu24-18072>
 - Katika, T., Koukoudis, K., Michalis, P., Ikiz Kaya, D., Guzman, P., Veiga-Pires, C., & Amditis, A. (2024, mars). Empowering Communities Through Digital Innovation and Crowdsourcing for Cultural Heritage Preservation. EGU General Assembly 2024 (EGU), Vienna, Austria. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu24-3517>
 - Ikiz Kaya, D., Guzman, P., Veiga-Pires, C., Oliveira, S., Katika, T., Veere Hoogbergen, A., Pulles, K., & Nicu, I. C. (2024, mars). Living Labs for participatory value, risk and impact assessments in coastal and underwater heritage sites. EGU General Assembly 2024 (EGU), Vienna, Austria. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu24-3132>
 - Nicu, I. C., Karamvavis, K., Karathanassi, V., & Guzman, P. (2024, mars). Monitoring an Arctic cultural heritage site with state-of-the-art remote sensing techniques – Lessons from the THETIDA project. EGU General Assembly 2024 (EGU), Vienna, Austria. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu24-3000>

3. EGU General Assembly 2024, Vienna, Austria (April 2024). Partners involved: ICCS, CCVAIlg, UAAlg, CIMA, UNIPD, NIKU, TU/e.

Organisation of a dedicated session with Climate Effect EU projects from the Green Cluster on Cultural Heritage. THETIDA submitted 4 presentations (see above) and displayed 3 posters. The posters were the following:

- Michalis, P., Mazzoli, C., Karathanassi, V., Ikiz Kaya, D., Martins, F., Cocco, M., Guy, A., & Amditis, A. (2024). THETIDA: Safeguarding and protecting Europe's coastal and underwater cultural heritage from the effects of climate change and natural hazards. EGU General Assembly 2024 (EGU), Vienna, Austria. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu24-2090>
- Garzon, J. L., Mills, L., & Martins, F. (2024). Operational hydrodynamic modeling as a tool to predict risks on underwater cultural heritage sites. Demonstration for the Algarve Coast. EGU General Assembly 2024 (EGU), Vienna, Austria. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu24-3913>
- Mazzoli, C., Cesareo, L. P., Coletti, C., Germinario, L., MARITAN, L., Ballarin, L., Moro, I., Demesticha, S., Martins, F., Ruberti, F., & Michalis, P. (2024). Effects of environmental stresses and climate change on the deterioration of underwater cultural heritage: the THETIDA approach. EGU General Assembly 2024 (EGU), Vienna, Austria. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu24-16558>

4. Technical Publications

- Mendonça F, Martins F, Janeiro J. SMS-Coastal, a New Python Tool to Manage MOHID-Based Coastal Operational Models. *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*. 2023; 11(8):1606. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jmse11081606>
- Chrysovalanta Alexopoulou, Vassilia Karathanassi, Maria Kremezi, Coastal Erosion Assessment for Protecting Cultural Heritage, July 2024, IGARSS.

5. Peer-reviewed journal publication

Nicu, I.C., Rubensdotter, L., Tanyaş, H. et al. Near Pan-Svalbard permafrost cryospheric hazards inventory (SvalCryo). *Sci Data* 11, 894 (2024). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-024-03754-7>

6. Participations in industrial exhibitions with booths

- EUDIShow 2023, Bologna, Italy (October 2023). Partners involved: IANTD, ELB, UNIPD.

- New European Bauhaus Festival, Brussels, Belgium (April 2024). Partner involved: ICCS.

7. Contributions and participations to scientific conversations

- Contribution to the Climate Change Emergencies & Cultural Heritage Speaker Series organized by CIFAL York, York University, UNITAR and Heritage Ottawa (Online – March 2024). Partner involved: TU/e
- Contribution at UNESCO presentation of the Veneto Stars Challenge: Space Data for Cultural Heritage and UNESCO Sites, Paris, France (March 2024). Partner involved: EURISY.
- Contribution to European Urban Resilience Forum, Valencia, Spain (June 2024). Partner involved: ICCS.
- Discussions on the Algarve pilot site (Portugal) and modelling work of THETIDA with the National Centre for Nautical and Underwater Archaeology (CNANS) and RECON Offshore (June 2024 and September 2024). Partners involved: UAlg, CIMA.

8. Technical workshops organised

Considering the description given in the Grant Agreement, technical workshops have been identified mainly as Living Labs organised in pilot sites but are not limited to Living Labs.

- Coordination Workshop in Svalbard, Norway (September 2023). Partner involved: NIKU.
- Living Labs Testing in the Netherlands during the ONGEZOUTEN (September 2023). Partners involved: MOOI, TU/e.
- Workshop at the Frysk Toerisme Kongers in the Netherlands on participation tools in the IJsselmeer area (March 2024). Partner involved: MOOI.
- 2 technical training sessions for experienced divers on 3D-shooting of underwater cultural heritage and data collection in La Spezia, Italy (August 2023). Partner involved: IANTD.
- Living Lab 1 in La Spezia, Italy (June 2024). Partners involved: IANTD, MDCA, ELB.
- Preparatory workshop on Living Labs in Cyprus (July 2024). Partners involved: CMMI, UCY.
- Living Lab 1 in Algarve, Portugal (September 2024). Partners involved: CIMA, UAlg, CCVAlg, NIKU, TU/e.

9. Online tutorial

THETIDA Training Workshop on Cultural Heritage and Climate Change, Living Labs, and Crowdsourcing Tools for Adaptation Strategies, held on 9 January 2024. Partners involved: TU/e, NIKU, CCVALg.

10. Participations in fairs and symposiums:

- Thessaloniki International Fair, Athens, Greece (September 2023). Partner involved: ICCS.
- Platformdag IJsselmeergebied, Lelystad, the Netherlands (November 2023). Partner involved: MOOI.
- Europe Day Event, Athens, Greece (May 2024). Partner involved: ICCS.
- TU/e Sustainability Day, Eindhoven, the Netherlands (September 2024). Partner involved: TU/e.
- European Researchers' Night, Athens, Greece (September 2024). Partners involved: ICCS, NTUA.

11. Participation to the Horizon Results Booster platform of the European Commission in the framework of the Green Cluster for Cultural Heritage. Climate Effect EU projects benefitted from two trainings on Intellectual Property Rights on 17 May 2024 and on 27 August 2024. Partners involved: EURISY, ICCS.

2.2.2 Updated reporting method for dissemination activities

To facilitate the reporting of dissemination activities undertaken by consortium partners, WP6 leader distributes monthly a table for WP partners to fill-in with the latest activities (see Annex 1), and report the results in the [KPIs Updates - FILLED BY WP6 LEADER.xlsx](#) table.

2.3 Updated Communication and Dissemination Channels and Tools

The table below provides an overview of the communication and dissemination channels and tools mentioned in D6.1 [1]. The channels and tools mentioned were selected according to and tailored to the needs of the three target audiences of the THETIDA project. Table 2 focuses on the channels and tools used from M00 to M18. A similar table comprising all mediums can be found in D6.1 [1].

Table 2. Tools and Channels Summary

Channels and Tools	Target			Purpose
	Target Audience n°1	Target Audience n°2	Target Audience n°3	
Visual Identity	•	•	•	Enhance project identity and branding.
Website	•	•	•	Provide information to online visitors about the project, its objectives, events and news, and enabling them to subscribe to the Newsletter.
Social Media	•	•	•	Allow real-time and continuous engagement with targeted audiences, as well as interactions with audiences and consortium partners.
e-Newsletters and e-Mail Campaigns	•	•	•	Engage with targeted audiences, announce events and update stakeholders about news related to the project in real-time.
General Media Spreading	•	•	•	Update local/regional/ national audiences about major developments regarding THETIDA.
Promotional Material	•	•	•	Facilitate project's promotion and information sharing during events (both internal and external).
Organisation and Attendance of/to Events	•	•	•	Share and promote the project and its results with target audiences.
Scientific Publications	•	•		Share THETIDA scientific developments and results within scientific communities to ensure adequate dissemination of aforementioned results.
Technical Publications	•	•		Share THETIDA technical developments and results within technical communities to ensure adequate dissemination of aforementioned results.
Q&A Platform	•	•		Ensure access to conversations about the project repository in reference sites.

Workshops and Trainings	• •	Train interested entities on the outcomes and results of the project.
Joint Dissemination Activities	• • •	Amplify and maximise the impact and outreach of the project's results.

2.3.1 Online Tools

a. Website

The website was designed to be easily navigable and accessible to online visitors. It serves as a repository of the activities carried out within the project, and gathers the material created, including publications, blog articles on events organised or attended, a presentation the project, its consortium partners and 7 pilot sites, as well as a list of deliverables.

As of October 1st 2024, the website has been visited by 3.1k unique visitors (referred as New Users in figures 3 and 4 below). It is worth noting that the most significant part of the traffic on the THETIDA project comes from direct search, *i.e.* users insert manually the THETIDA website URL in their search engines. It can be deduced from these numbers that online visitors intentionally search for the project online to gain additional information. Thus, demonstrating the positive impact of communication and dissemination activities on awareness raising and engagement with the project.

Regarding user attributes, a third of THETIDA new users have been identified as coming from the United States of America. It was reported by CIMA and UAIG that the story behind the B-24 Liberator and the crash of American soldiers during WWII along the coast of Algarve triggered a specific interest from American authorities and citizens. Additionally, Greece, Italy, the Netherlands, Cyprus, Portugal, and France have been identified as the other main countries of user acquisitions, reflecting the nationality of consortium partners and the location of pilot sites.

Figure 3. Screenshot of New Users (THETIDA website – Google Analytics)

Sessions by Session primary channel group ...

SESSION PRIMARY CHAN...	SESSIONS
Direct	3K
Organic Search	1K
Organic Social	638
Referral	407
Unassigned	23

Figure 4. Screenshot of Traffic Acquisition (THETIDA Website – Google Analytics)

Figure 5. User Attributes (THETIDA Website - Google Analytics)

b. Social Media channels

The social media channels of the THETIDA project are tracked monthly by WP6 leader since M05 (September 2023) to assess the progress made, the evolution of the communication and outreach activities, and devise new strategies. Consortium partners can access the reporting table at all times on the SharePoint of the project: [KPIs Updates - FILLED BY WP6 LEADER.xlsx](#).

All the numbers mentioned in this section were collected on **October 1st, 2024**.

The following channels have been used to implement communication strategies:

- A **TikTok** account (@thetida.project) was created in July 2024 and will be managed by ICCS with the support of WP6 leader. The THETIDA TikTok account totalises 15 followers, and 3 published videos (figures 6 and 7).

Figure 6. Screenshot of the THETIDA TikTok Key Metrics (24/10/2024)

Figure 7. Screenshot of the THETIDA TikTok Channel (21/10/2024)

- Instagram:** The @thetida_project account comprises 80 publications, with a total of 110 followers, and an average of 331 impressions per month with the content published. The audience of the THETIDA Instagram account is composed mainly of women from 25 to 45 years old from Greece (Fig. 8).

Figure 8. Instagram Publications with Most Engagement

Figure 9 displays 5 Instagram publications with most engagement from May 2023 to 1st October 2024.

- Facebook:** The @Thetida account totalises 125 publications, 335 followers, and an average of 2,738 impressions per month with the content published. The main audience of the THETIDA Facebook channel is composed of men from 45 to 64 years old, coming from Italy (Fig. 10). The Facebook page gathers most of the diving community. Emphasizing this effect, the THETIDA project regularly publishes in the following Facebook groups: Maritime Archaeology News, Centre for Maritime Archaeology, and Digital Archaeology Group. Figure 11 displays 5 Facebook publications with most engagement from May 2023 to 1st October 2024.

Figure 10. Demographics of Facebook Followers

Figure 11. Facebook Publications with Most Engagement

- X:** The @Thetida_project has cumulated a total of 222 followers, with 177 posts published and an average of 1,196 impressions per month from September 2023 to June 2024. Since June 2024, a change in the platform's policy no longer allows access to its analytics for the THETIDA project, as a paid membership is now required.
- LinkedIn:** The @THETIDA account cumulates a total of 597 followers, 128 publications and an average of 3,739 impressions per month (Fig. 12). From October 2023 to October 2024, the data shows that a majority (14,5%) of the followers are working in research, followed by 7,6% in higher education, and 7,3% in computer services and consultancy (Fig. 13). 10,2% of followers live in Athens and its periphery (Greece), 4,3% live in the Metropolitan area of Delhi (India), and 3% of them live in La Randstad in the Netherlands (Fig. 14). The present numbers highlight the diversity of the THETIDA online community and its relevance with regards to the audiences targeted.

Figure 12. LinkedIn Followers Statistics from 21 October 2023 to 1st October 2024

Données démographiques des abonnés ⓘ

Figure 13. LinkedIn Followers Demographics by Sector

Données démographiques des abonnés ⓘ

Figure 14. LinkedIn Followers Demographics
by Location

YouTube: The three videos posted on the @THETIDA YouTube channel cumulate 199 views in total, and the channel is followed by 17 accounts.

c. e-Newsletters

Quarterly e-newsletters dedicated to the activities carried within the framework of the THETIDA project and to the progresses made in the project are being sent quarterly since M06. A total of 4 THETIDA-labelled newsletters have been sent during this reporting period to up to 85 contact points, with an opening rate of 55% and only one unsubscribed (Fig. 15). The most performant newsletter was sent in May 2024 and reached an opening rate of 61% (Fig. 16).

Figure 15. e-Newsletters Performances

Individual message performance

Figure 16. Individual e-Newsletters Performances

Complementing the THETIDA-labelled newsletters, consortium partners distributed newsletters introducing THETIDA and its achievements:

- IANTD sent a total of 5 e-newsletters in Italian: Bollettini Istruttori n°52, 53, 54, 55 from July 2023 to May 2024, and an *ad-hoc* edition dedicated to the Living Lab held in La Spezia (Italy) in June 2024.
- EURISY sent 4 e-newsletters mentioning the THETIDA project from October 2023 to July 2024.
- UAlg presented the THETIDA project in the January 2024 edition of the UAlgZine (Revista da Universidade do Algarve n°16, p.43).

d. General Media Spreading and Press Releases

As proposed within D6.1, results and non-confidential information about the project have been promoted through online publishing platforms and magazines, newspapers, and other media to raise awareness on THETIDA [1].

- A total of 8 unique contributions in 8 different blogs were made. Contributions include the presentation of the THETIDA project within the websites of the following consortium partners: [ICCS](#), [CIMA](#), [ELB](#), [NIKU](#), [EURISY](#), [MOOI](#), [CMMI](#). THETIDA was also mentioned within the website of the [ENGINEER project](#).
- 11 press releases were distributed during this reporting period in both English and national languages: 1 press release in Greek distributed by ICCS, 1 THETIDA-labelled press release in English, 4 press releases in Portuguese distributed by CIMA and CCVAI in Portuguese online medias, 5 press releases distributed by EdgeLab before THETIDA General Assembly in June 2024 in local newspapers and in *Sole 24 Ore*, as well as a presentation of the project in one local TV program.
- Publication in [SUB Underwater Magazine](#) by IANTD in August 2024. SUB is a reference magazine for technical divers in Italy, showcasing diving expeditions taking place in Italy and beyond (Fig. 17).

Figure 17. Cover of SUB Magazine featuring the Equa Shipwreck

2.3.2 Offline tools

a. Communication Material

While in line with the visual identity created in the early stages of the project, the communication material developed in the next steps of the project will aim to showcase the material gathered by partners, such as pictures of the pilot sites, and visuals of the solutions developed.

To support the diffusion of the material gathered and to complement the materials created during the initial stage of the project, an additional banner has been created (Fig. 18).

Figure 18. Second Version Banner

b. Organisation and Attendance to in-person Events

THETIDA consortium partners have organised 28 internal events and attended 19 external events from May 2023 to October 2024, as described above. As mentioned in D6.1, events are divided into two categories. Internal events, encompass local, regional, and international events organised by consortium partners [1]. On average, 60 persons attended the events organised by demo leaders. External events are local, regional and international events where consortium partners participate in as exhibitors or speakers for instance. Details on the activities undertaken are mentioned above.

Internal events include:

- 20 events organised by demo leaders, including 16 diving training sessions organised by IANTD, 1 workshop organised by CCVALg during Portuguese week of Science and Technology, 1 meeting organised by UAlg with the National Center for Nautical and Underwater Archaeology (CNANS) and RECON Offshore, 2 events organised by IANTD for divers.
- 8 technical workshops, including 2 organised in Svalbard and IJsselmeer in September 2023, 1 workshop at Frysk Toerisme Kongers (March 2024), 2 technical diving workshops (Mars 2024), Living Labs 1 organised in Italy (June 2024) and Portugal (September 2024), and a preparatory workshop organised in Cyprus in July 2024.

External events include participation in (including presentations and posters):

- 10 scientific conferences: Cyprus Bicomunal Sustainability Conference 2023, CYMON 2024, Panhellenic Conferences on Digital Cultural Heritage 2024, EGU General Assembly 2024, ECSD8, SOMA 2024 XXV Symposium on Mediterranean Archaeology, Encontro de Oceanografia of Associação Portuguesa de Oceanografia (APOCEAN) 2024, THALASSA 2024, IGARSS 2024, EnoLL Open Living Labs Days 2024.
- 2 industrial exhibitions with booths: EUDIShow 2023, New European Bauhaus Festival 2024.
- 3 scientific conversations: during the presentation of the VeneTo Stars Challenge: Space Data for Cultural Heritage and UNESCO Sites, at European Urban Resilience Forum 2024, during a meeting held with American maritime archaeologists in Algarve, at European Researchers' Night 2024.
- 4 fairs and symposiums: Thessaloniki International Fair 2023, Platformdag IJsselmeergebied 2023, TU/e Sustainability Day 2024, European Researchers' Night 2024, European Researchers' Night2024.

2.4 Updated Exploitation Plan

As stated in D6.1, the general strategy for the exploitation of the THETIDA project relies mainly on the effective dissemination of results and outcomes, and of their proper exploitation by targeted groups [1]. The exploitation of the THETIDA project is led by Task 6.4 Coherent Business Model(s), Exploitation Activities and Market-entry Preparation Plan, under the supervision of ELB. While the deliverable for this task is not due until the end of the project (M36) partners involved in task 6.4 prepared a preliminary Business Model Canvas to be complemented according to the development of the project and serving as a basis for a more detailed exploitation plan.

2.4.1 THETIDA Business Model Canvas

The Business Model Canvas was selected for the THETIDA project as it provides a well-organized, visual framework for describing, analysing, and designing business models in a simple and accessible way. The canvas breaks down a business into nine fundamental building blocks, helping teams systematically address the key aspects of value creation, delivery, and capture [2]. This approach is particularly helpful in a multi-disciplinary project such as THETIDA, where collaboration among stakeholders, researchers, and institutions requires clarity and an unified understanding of the business model.

The framework promotes creativity, ensures alignment among partners, and facilitates the adaptation of the business strategy based on evolving market needs or project outcomes. By using the canvas, communication of the project's objectives, resources, and value propositions to external stakeholders and funders is facilitated in a comprehensive and intuitive way.

Figure 19. First Version of the THETIDA Business Model Canvas

The primary objective of the Business Model Canvas is to clearly define and structure the key elements necessary for the successful exploitation of the project. This involves identifying and analysing several core aspects of the business model, including:

- Key Partnerships:** The relationships with external parties, such as suppliers, collaborators, or strategic alliances, that will be crucial for the development and scaling of the project. The goal is to build strong partnerships that can enhance value creation and efficiency.
- Key Activities:** The essential tasks and operations that the business must undertake to deliver its value proposition. These activities are critical in ensuring the business achieves its mission and meets the needs of its customers.
- Value Proposition:** The unique value the project offers to its customers or stakeholders. It includes innovations in technology, improvements in efficiency, cost-effectiveness, or any other competitive advantage that distinguishes the project from others in the market.
- Customer Relationships:** The strategies for managing customer interactions and engagement. This includes understanding how relationships with customers will be nurtured, whether through personalized services, automated support, or other channels that will foster long-term relationships and loyalty.
- Customer Segments:** Identifying the target audience or market segments that will benefit most from the project's offerings. Understanding the needs, behaviours, and preferences of these segments is vital for aligning the value proposition with market demands.

- **Key Resources:** The assets, both tangible and intangible, that are necessary to support the business operations. These could include physical resources like equipment or technological infrastructure, human resources, or intellectual property such as patents or trademarks.
- **Channels:** The pathways through which the business will deliver its products or services to its customers. This could be through direct sales, online platforms, distributors, or other means that ensure the offering reaches the intended market effectively.
- **Cost Structure:** An analysis of the costs associated with operating the business, including fixed and variable costs, and how they align with the overall strategy to remain profitable. This will involve a detailed understanding of the expenses involved in production, marketing, and customer support.
- **Revenue Streams:** Identifying how the business will generate income. This could include direct sales, subscriptions, licensing fees, or other monetization strategies that align with the value provided to customers.

The asset of this business plan lies in determining the economic feasibility of the project by evaluating projected cash flows, calculating the break-even point, and assessing the risks and profit potential associated with the initiative. A comprehensive understanding of these factors will guide the decision-making process and help optimize the allocation of resources for sustainable growth.

2.4.2 Progress achieved during the reporting period

Task 6.4 partners have completed the first seven components of the Business Model Canvas and identified customers, stakeholders, and partners from a business-oriented perspective:

- **Customers:** are buying THETIDA services and/or products. The customer does not necessarily match the user. For instance, local businesses could be customers buying our products/services to attract tourists (users) who are their customers. Are only considered as customers those who have sufficient budget.
- **Stakeholders:** are anyone having an interest in the project that can influence or be affected by THETIDA. They can be customers, users, suppliers, partners, communities, governments, etc.
- **Partners:** are a specific category of stakeholders who can positively affect the project, providing resources, both material and immaterial. They can have a monetary or non-monetary return.

1. Customer Segments:

Customer segments have been carefully identified based on their financial capacity to support the project. Task partners categorize these as:

- **Local Public Authorities:** This includes municipalities and regional authorities interested in creating tourist attractions to enhance local hospitality. Their goal is to stimulate economic growth by promoting the region's natural and cultural heritage.
- **Local Business Owners:** These stakeholders, tied closely to the community, seek to foster local relationships and increase visibility. They see the project as a means to drive regional growth and align with sustainability efforts.
- **National Public Authorities:** Including entities such as the Ministry of Cultural Heritage, the Ministry of Environment, and the Ministry of Tourism. These authorities focus on heritage preservation and environmental sustainability and have access to significant resources to support such initiatives.

2. Value Proposition:

The value proposition has been tailored for each segment:

- **Local Public Authorities:**
 - Monitoring and measuring environmental factors like water variables for sustainability, including metabolic rates, photosynthesis, dissolved oxygen, pH, and salinity.
 - Climate change monitoring and assessing post-event damage, such as flooding.
 - Coastal erosion and underwater cultural heritage (UCH) protection.
 - Risk analysis and impact assessment aimed at boosting local GDP and improving public awareness about UCH.
- **Local Business Owners:**
 - New business opportunities and revenue generation through tourism and cultural initiatives.
 - Strengthening local ties and improving brand visibility and community engagement.
- **National Public Authorities:**
 - Focused on climate change, risk analysis, and environmental impact assessments.
 - Aiding GDP improvement and fostering a broader public understanding and concern for UCH.

3. Key Partners:

Task partners have identified essential partners who will support the project's objectives, including:

- **Environmental Organizations (NGOs):** These groups focus on marine conservation and can help align the project with environmental goals.
- **Government Agencies:** Key players in environmental and maritime affairs who can assist with policy support and funding.
- **Research Institutions:** Universities and research centres that provide the scientific backing necessary for marine and archaeological studies.
- **International Organizations:** Such as UNESCO, providing global visibility and support for cultural preservation.
- **Industry Partners:** Marine technology companies and sustainable development experts who offer technical expertise and product support.

4. Key Resources:

Identified key resources include:

- **Investors:** Sourcing financial resources through public and private investors, grants, and loans.
- **Legal Support:** Ensuring compliance with regulations and securing intellectual property rights.
- **Technology and Equipment:** Specialized equipment for underwater archaeology, data collection, and artifact analysis.
- **Expertise:** Collaboration with experts in marine archaeology, conservation, and underwater exploration.
- **Public Awareness and Education:** Building relationships and promoting awareness about marine conservation and heritage.

5. Customer Relationships:

Building strong relationships through:

- **After-sales services:** Providing comprehensive support and maintenance for the products and services offered.
- **Marketing support:** Helping customers promote the project's initiatives.
- **Training:** Offering customized training to ensure effective use of the provided technology.
- **Data Analysis and Reporting:** Delivering detailed analytics to help customers interpret data and make informed decisions.

6. Channels:

Task partners plan to use both online and traditional marketing channels:

- Online Marketing: Website, social media platforms, email campaigns, and content marketing.
- Traditional Marketing: Participating in industry-specific events and partnerships with universities, museums, and research institutions.
- Events and Workshops: Engaging with customers through webinars, workshops, and conferences to promote our solutions and foster relationships.

7. Key Activities:

Key activities at this stage include:

- Market Research and Competitive Analysis: To assess the market potential and competitors.
- Brand Awareness: Initiating marketing campaigns to increase the visibility of the project.
- SWOT Analysis: Understanding strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats to position the project effectively in the market.

These activities are essential for defining the project's cost structure and revenue streams, which will guide financial decisions and ensure long-term sustainability.

2.4.3 Next steps

In the coming months, T6.4 efforts will focus on establishing a detailed and structured approach to market analysis, competitive landscape evaluation, and a comprehensive SWOT analysis. To ensure a robust understanding of the industry, Porter's Five Forces model will be leveraged to assess key strengths, competitive pressures, and market dynamics [3]. It will help identify barriers to entry, the influence of suppliers, the potential for substitute products, and the intensity of industry rivalry, enabling a strategic view of THETIDA's positioning.

Upon completing these assessments, the focus will shift to developing a clear financial model. Task partners will carefully estimate both fixed and variable costs, forecast potential revenue streams, and evaluate different pricing strategies to understand the economic viability of the THETIDA venture. Analysing these cost and revenue drivers, will enable to form a realistic view of the business's profitability, break-even points, and long-term financial sustainability.

As a final step, findings will be implemented through practical applications, focusing on the effective exploitation of identified opportunities. This phase will involve fine-tuning the strategy, launching initiatives based on market feedback, and ensuring that the business plan remains aligned with both internal goals and external market conditions.

Figure 20. Summary of Exploitation Next Actions

3. Evaluation of Communication and Dissemination Activities

To present the impact of the communication and dissemination strategy and activities established for the THETIDA project, the criteria stated in D6.1 were implemented [1].

To assess the status of communication and dissemination activities, discuss the impact of the activities and prepare the next steps at WP level, monthly WP meetings were organised during the reporting period to ensure coordination and cooperation of the activities at project level.

Following the first technical review meeting, actions were undertaken to highlight publications within peer-reviewed journals. Additionally, the website was updated to ensure accessibility to people with impairments.

The following table summarises the KPIs targets as mentioned in the Grant Agreement and provides a detailed assessment of the status of the KPIs at the end of the first reporting period (M18). As D6.2 is due for M18, the data included in the table does not contain the activities carried during October 2024.

Table 3. Evaluation of Communication and Dissemination KPIs

	Affiliated Channel and Tool	Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)	THETIDA Target Value	Values as of 1 st October 2024	Status and Explanation
KPIs to be reported on by M18	Social Media and Website	Total amount of followers	>2,000 by M18 and >5,000 by M36	1,296 (on LinkedIn, Instagram, Facebook, Twitter, YouTube, TikTok)	Not reached – High targets in Grant Agreement (issue reported to project coordinator)
		Publications on LinkedIn, Instagram, Facebook	2 posts per week	LinkedIn: 2,4 (128 publications) Instagram: 1,5 (80 publications) Facebook: 2,3 (125 publications)	On track
		Publications on Twitter	4 posts per week	3,3 (177 publications)	On track
		Videos uploaded on YouTube	4	3	On track – A fourth video has been published in the first half of October.
		Podcasts uploaded	>2	0	Not reached – Podcasts are targeting specific and expert audiences that were not primarily targeted during the reporting period. Additionally, content for qualitative podcast on the achievements of the project was not sufficient.

	Unique visitors on website	> 1,500 unique visitors	3,100	Exceeded
General Spreading	Newsletter and mailing-list contact points	>1,000	87	Not reached - High targets in GA (issue reported to project coordinator)
	Newsletters distributed	>3	14: 4 THETIDA-labelled, and 5 from IANTD, 4 from Eurisy, 1 from UAlg	Exceeded
	Press releases issued	>7	11	Exceeded
	Contributions to (10) different blogs	>12	8 in 8 blogs	Not reached – Difficulties in engaging some of the consortium partners.
Events	Events organised by demo leaders	>20	20	Reached
	Persons per event	>100	Average of 60 persons per event	Not reached – Most of the events organised by demo leaders are targeting specific audiences and local stakeholders and do not reach the 100 persons threshold.
	Printed materials distributed	>1,200	861	Not reached – When attending events, partners have been prioritising presentations of the THETIDA project rather than participation at booth.

KPIs to be reported by M36					Booths are known to foster the distribution of printed material.	
		Roll-up banners	>2	2	Reached	
	Dissemination Efforts		Publications in peer-reviewed journal	>8	1	On track – publications in peer-reviewed journals are expected for the second half of the project.
			Presentations in scientific conferences	>16	14	On track (and expected to be exceeded by M36).
			Technical publications	>25	2	On track – Most technical publications will be made available in the second half of the project.
			Participations in industrial exhibitions with booth	>3	2	On track
			Available deliverables	>13	3	Not reached – the number of public deliverables does not match the target value mentioned in the Grant Agreement.
			Repositories used for source code publication	2	0	On track
			Contribution/participation to scientific conversations	>25	4	On track – Further contributions and participations to scientific conversations are expected to take place from M18 to M36 with further achievements.

	Technical workshops organised in different countries	>10 in 7 different countries	7 in 5 countries	On track
	Webinars organised	>6	0	On track – Webinars have been structured from M18 to M36.
	Online training tutorials	>8	1	On track – Online trainings require the further development of THETIDA solutions.
	Participation in fairs/symposiums	>9	4	On track
	Standards contributions to different organisations	>5	0	On track – Standards contributions are expected to be distributed to organisations from M24 to M36.
	Policy recommendations	>5	0	On track – Policy recommendations are expected to be distributed from M24 to M36.

Over 27 KPIs, 17 are on track or reached, 7 are not reached, and 3 exceeded. The following table presents the strategies and mitigation actions planned considered to reach unreached targets, it was presented during the Executive Board meeting held on 10 October 2024:

Table 4. Mitigation Measures to Unreached Targets

N°	Targets not reached	Mitigation measures
1	Total amount of followers	Increase communication activities on social media channels with attractive and qualitative content.
2	Mailing list contact points	Encourage consortium partners to add registration link to forms distributed and to invitation to events. https://bit.ly/thetida-newsletter
3	Podcasts	Structure podcast content on non-confidential achievements. A first series of podcast will be made available in December 2024.
4	Contributions to different blogs	Invite consortium partners to share information on THETIDA on their respective websites.
5	Persons per events organised by demo leaders	While specific events organised by demo leaders require smaller groups of people to facilitate information sharing and exchanges, consortium partners should balance with the organisation of larger scale events.
6	Printed material distributed	Print and distribute more material. Strengthen reporting of material distribution.
7	Deliverables available	The number of public deliverables does not match the target value mentioned in the Grant Agreement. The issue was reported to project coordinator.

4. Next Steps

In the next 18 months, the main communication and dissemination actions will consist of:

- The implementation of the mitigation measures detailed in D6.2 to ensure the effective achievements of KPIs targeted by the Grant Agreement.
- The organisation of 6 webinars led by ICCS with the support of EURISY. An initial structure has been established with the support of WP6 partners.
- The preparation, recording, and publication of podcasts on the THETIDA project. The first foreseen series of podcasts will aim to introduce the Inspiring Women behind the THEITDA project and will be distributed from December 2024 onwards.
- The structure of additional campaigns to increase the number of contact points on the mailing list and reinforcement of consortium partners support in sharing the registration link.
- The development of campaigns to increase the online community on THETIDA social media platforms with qualitative content on the non-confidential results of the project and targeting engaging individuals to create a snow-ball effect.
- The creation of a series of 7 short videos on the THETIDA pilot sites for YouTube, Instagram, Facebook, and TikTok.
- The continuous update of the THETIDA website as the project progresses and activities take place.
- The further development of the exploitation strategy supporting the THETIDA project as abovementioned.
- The creation of additional communication material to reflect the progresses of the project and highlight the content created by consortium partners when leading THETIDA activities.
- Further participation to the Horizon Results Booster platform of the European Commission within the framework of the Green Cluster for Cultural Heritage, including the creation of a logo, single URL address, and policy brief.

5. Conclusions

The communication, dissemination, and exploitation efforts of the THETIDA project focus on achieving the set objectives of the project. Throughout the reporting period, the performed activities demonstrate a satisfactory progress, as indicated by improvements in various KPIs, deepening community involvement, and active participation from various stakeholders.

Up to M18 most of the targets set have been achieved or are on track to be met. However, some of the metrics (*e.g.* social media followers, mailing list contact points, and number of blogs contributed in) are below expected performance. The primary factors are the ambitious engagement targets included in the Grant Agreement and the ensuing challenges of available resources and logistics.

Mitigation measures have been discussed and planned in an effort to increase visibility and engagement with both online and physical audiences. With the planned increase in range of content (*e.g.* podcasts, webinars, additional publications) the considerable targets are expected to be achieved. Enhanced outreach as well as tailored strategies will help achieve the overall objective of the project, *i.e.* fostering an enduring impact on cultural heritage preservation in response to climate and environmental challenges.

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Annex 1: Dissemination KPIs Table

DISSEMINATION KPIs – DEFINITION TABLE

For clarity and to avoid double counting, please assign **one event to one category/KPI** according to your personal assessment of the event main characteristics.

Definitions established in this document only serve the purposes of this document and of the tracking of KPIs within the THETIDA project.

KPIs	Definition	FILLED BY PROJECT PARTNERS	
		Numerical reporting of KPIs executed in the last month	Dates and Remarks/Details
Unique contributions/publications in different blogs	Number of articles published in open communities, blog, non-profit organizations and channels such as Gitter Communities, Nature.com, and DownToEarth.		
Printed Material distributed	Number of paper-based promotional instruments distributed when participating in events, including brochures, catalogues, posters, and any other resource.		
Press Releases	Number of press releases distributed, including press releases translated and distributed in national languages.		
Events organised by demo leaders	Number of events organised by members of THETIDA consortium partners. This KPI includes: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • THETIDA-labelled events as well as non-THETIDA-labelled events organised by partners on THETIDA relevant topics such as coastal and underwater archaeology, diving, environment, search and rescue activities and others, with a participation of THETIDA project. 		

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Events organised in national languages and can be held either online or in-person. 		
Persons per event organised by demo leaders	Total number of audiences attending the event. The KPI sums up both in person and online attendance.		
Publications in scientific peer-reviewed open-access journals	Number of scientific publications disseminating new information, data and results, and aiming to further the progress of science. <i>E.g.</i> , International Journal of Nautical Archaeology, Journal of Cultural Heritage, Air&Space Europe, etc.		
Presentations in scientific conferences	Number of THETIDA labelled presentations at scientific conferences. <i>E.g.</i> , EGU, IGARSS Symposium.		
Technical publications	Number of THETIDA publications including blog posts, articles, position/white papers, catalogues, books, which are not included in scientific publications or unique contributions.		
Participation in industrial exhibitions with booths	Number of participations in national or international exhibitions, with a THETIDA booth or a major THETIDA contribution in a partner's booth.		
Publicly available deliverables	Number of THETIDA deliverables published in source code platforms (Zenodo and GitHub). Reference deliverables that you made accessible (title) in remarks.		
Publication of source code in 2 different repositories	Mention the repository(/ies) name(s) when filling this line.		

Contribution/participation to scientific conversations	Number of participations to panel discussions and round tables where there is no dedicated THETIDA presentation/poster, but the project is mentioned.		
Organisation of technical workshops	Number of workshops organised and held to present the progresses of the project (to the public).		
Organisation of webinars	Number of webinars organised and, depending on confidentiality requirements, distributed on THETIDA's online platforms (mainly website and YouTube).		
Organisation of online training tutorials	Number of online training tutorials organised and animated internally with pilot sites partners to train local partners on THETIDA services and products (e.g., Living Labs, tools and devices developed within the project, etc.).		
Participation in fairs/symposiums	Number of participations in fairs and symposiums, including participation in work streams and joint dissemination activities with international and local partners (e.g. Svalbard Museum, Algarve Tourism Board, etc.).		
Number of banners used, and brochures distributed at fairs/symposiums attended	Number of promotional instruments distributed during fair/symposiums by mentioning the type of instrument distributed. If you used different promotional instruments, such as t-shirt, bottles, bags and others, please mention them as well.		
Standards contributions to different organisations	Number of standards participations and contributions, <i>i.e.</i> participations and cooperations in the establishment of standards with standards		

	developing organisations, certification committees, open-source communities, relevant public bodies.		
Policy recommendations	Number of project results shared with policy makers at local, national and European levels to support the definition of future Research and Innovation directions based on the project's acquired knowledge.		